

”We” ecosystem : a proposal for the futur of search engine and discovery tools

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Abstract

This keynote is a proposal to define a new ecosystem and plateform, called “We”, that places the practices of researchers in SSH at the heart of search engine and discovery tools features. The keynote will first situate the “We” proposal in the ecosystem of and for academic tools. Secondly, it will propose a conceptual representation for an innovative platform based on the discovery of experts, topics and trends for scientific information using classification, linking and enrichment of data tools. It will finally describe its notions (expert, Topic box) and functionalities such as integrated tools (Python notebooks) and technological advances (Deep Learning). We want to point out that this proposal provides a big picture, which ideas are yet to be discussed and enriched. In particular, the different diagrams do not pretend to present an exact design of the HMI but instead aim at illustrating its forseen functionalities. As a proposal, “We” might be implemented for any academic search engines, such as ISIDORE as a primary proof of concept, then eventually as a seamless service. This presentation will rely on recent research works developed by HN-Lab team of IR* Huma-Num through projects like “Revue 2.0”, “Huma-num Open Science” and some proofs of concept like Callisto, ISIDORE Jupyter Notebooks, ISIDORE connectors for Zotero.

Table of presentation

A brief history of search engine in SSH

From discovery tools to research assistant platform

“We” in a nutshell : a next step for ISIDORE platform

Bibliography

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